

Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome Trust

Clinical Research Programme

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STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE	MLW.SOP.Tentacle.01 Version 01
Standard Operating Procedures for field and laboratory work for the TENTACLE study	
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**MALAWI-LIVERPOOL-WELLCOME TRUST
CLINICAL RESEARCH PROGRAMME
APPROVED ORIGINAL**

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1. BACKGROUND

This work will use a 'One Health' approach to investigate the transmission dynamics and diversity of *E. coli* and NTS between humans, animals and the environment within the household unit. *E. coli* is a ubiquitous commensal bacteria present in the gastrointestinal tract of all animals, including humans. As such, it is perfectly placed to act as an indicator of microbial connectivity within an ecological niche, and as a reservoir of antimicrobial resistance genes. NTS causes a greater threat to human health in sub-Saharan Africa (ssa) than other settings, largely due to invasive disease. Both of these bacteria are transmitted by the faeco-oral route. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global public health threat that is likely to impact most severely on low and middle income countries (LMICs). There is a need to identify the transmission routes for these bacteria and AMR determinants; currently this concept has not yet been investigated in rural areas of sub-Saharan Africa. This study proposes to investigate whether or not the household is a distinct "unit" of transmission for these bacteria in Malawi.

2. PURPOSE

This SOP describes fieldwork techniques in order to collect stool from animals and humans, as well as environmental sample collection.

The second part of the SOP describes selective culture of stool and environmental samples to enable detection of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella*.

The third part of the SOP describes the SOP for antimicrobial susceptibility testing and storage of cultured isolates and plate sweeps.

3. RESPONSIBILITY

Fieldworkers

- Collection of clinical samples from humans and animals in accordance with the Sample Collection SOPs
- Collection of environmental samples in accordance with the Sample Collection SOPs.
- Correct labelling of clinical samples
- Prompt transport of clinical samples to laboratory
- Completion of sample collection log

Study Laboratory Technicians

- Receive samples from field and complete sample collection log
- Register samples on Project Spreadsheet
- Double-check correct sample labelling
- Processing stool samples in accordance with this SOP
- Storage of samples for further analysis in accordance with this SOP

Principal Investigators

- Ensure fieldwork training in sample collection provided.
- Manage fieldwork and decide which animals and environmental samples will be taken.
- Ensure laboratory training in sample processing procedures provided.
- Undertake quality control checks of laboratory processing.

4. PROCEDURE

Fieldwork Methods

- **Day 1**

Houses will be visited once by the field team during the week prior to sample collection. The purpose of this visit will be to:

1. Discuss the study with the Head of the Household and household members and obtain informed consent and assent as necessary.
2. Assess how many domestic and livestock animals are kept in the household.
3. Assess locations for environmental sampling, bird nets and rodent traps.

At this visit the study will be discussed with the household head, and it will be made clear the plan for Day 2 and Day 3 sampling which will occur the Monday and Tuesday the following week.

Timeframes for sample collection which will be useful for the Head of the Household to know will be clarified.

- **Day 2 (Aim to arrive at the household between 2-4pm)**

1. Further clarification of the study protocol if necessary for the household members.
2. Start the Household questionnaires with the Head of the Household and household members if present.
3. The Head of the Household should complete the main questionnaire.
4. Each individual household member, including the Head of the Household should complete the Individual Household member questionnaire

Sample collection at each household will take place over a two-day period.

Species	Day 2	Day 3
Humans	Obtain informed consent from Head of Household and household members.	Household questionnaire will be completed.

	Leave faecal sample containers at household for collection of human faecal samples.	Collect filled faecal sample pots from human household members.
Domestic animals, livestock, poultry		Collect faecal samples and cloacal swabs from domestic animals, livestock, poultry, rodents, wild birds.
		Collect blood from mammals and poultry post faecal sampling.
Wild birds and bats	Place tarpaulins for overnight collection of wild bird or bat faeces overnight.	Collect faeces deposited on tarpaulins overnight.
		Early morning; erect bird nets and collect cloacal swabs from any birds restrained in nets.
Rodents	Place humane rodent traps around household.	Collect a faecal samples from the rodents found in traps.
Geckos	Teach household members to recognize characteristic gecko faeces.	Collect filled faecal sample pots containing gecko faecal samples.

	Leave faecal sample containers at household for collection of gecko faecal samples by household members	If no gecko faeces have been collected overnight, collect gecko faeces from around the household area.
Environment		Collect flies in sterile bottle, swabs of food preparation, eating and latrine areas

Faecal sample collection

- **Human samples**

Fieldworkers will leave sample containers for each human study participant in the household on day 1 of sampling. These will be clearly labelled to identify which container should be used for each participant. Participants will be given biodegradable bowls and sample containers with spoons to facilitate collection of the sample. The bowls can be disposed of in a pit latrine or collected by the field team and incinerated on day 2. Families will be given sealable opaque “freezer bags” or similar in which to store samples whilst waiting for collection. Samples will be collected the following day (Day 2).

- **Domestic animal and livestock samples**

This will include dogs, cats, poultry, sheep, goats, cattle, pigs.

On day 2 faeces (2-20g) will be collected per rectum by Fieldworkers and placed into appropriately labelled individual sample containers. Appropriate Personal Protective Equipment including wellington boots and protective gloves will be used for sample collection. Animals will be appropriately restrained by trained personnel during sample collection. Ectoparasites noted on these animals will be collected into sterile bijoux containers.

- **Poultry**

This will include chickens, ducks, geese, guinea fowl, turkeys.

Domestic poultry will be sampled on the morning of day 2 prior to release from the overnight housing. Poultry will be appropriately restrained and a cloacal swab will be obtained per rectum. Number, species, breed, age estimate and sex of the poultry will be documented at this time and any clinical abnormalities of the poultry will be noted.

- **Peri-domestic wildlife samples**

Rodents

Using an established method, humane rodent traps will be left in appropriate locations within the household (and location recorded) on day 1 and left in place overnight. Rectal swabs will be taken from any rodents collected in traps on day 2 and any free faeces within the traps will be collected. The species, sex and general appearance of the rodent will be recorded and a faecal sample will be taken directly per rectum. Any ectoparasites noted on the rodents will be collected into sterile bijoux containers and killed and preserved in a 70% ethanol solution.

Geckos

Household members will be taught how to collect gecko excreta on day 1 of sampling at each household and appropriate sterile faecal sample containers will be left with the household to be filled overnight prior to collection of the pot on day 2. The characteristic excreta will be collected as it is deposited around the household and placed into appropriate sterile containers.

Wild-birds

Bird nets will be placed around the outside of each household for a 2-3 hour period between 4am-7am on day 2 of sampling. Birds captured in the nets will be appropriately handled by trained fieldworkers, and a cloacal swab will be taken to collect fresh faeces. If appropriate, clean tarpaulins will be placed underneath roosts located within the household perimeter on day 1 and left in place overnight. Any faeces deposited on the

tarpaulins by wild birds will be collected on day 2 of sampling. Tarpaulins may also be used to collect bat faeces from bats located within the perimeter of the household.

○ **Environmental samples**

Environmental samples will be collected in the form of flies manually collected in a sterile pot, sterile swabs will be used to sample household members' hands, clothes and the surfaces of eating and sleeping areas. Water samples will be taken from water stored within the household.

Return to the laboratory

- Once collected, all samples will be placed in a cool box, chilled to a temperature of approximately 4°C.
- Samples will be transported to the laboratory to begin processing within four hours of collection.

Laboratory Protocol

1. ***Salmonella* Isolation** (max number of samples 50)
(we are assuming approx. 10% prevalence of NTS)

Day 1

SUMMARY: Incubate all samples in enrichment broth

- A) Process the samples as soon as possible after returning to the laboratory, definitely within 4hrs.
- B) Decontaminate the work bench with Virkon and 70% ethanol.
- C) If solid stool, add 1g of faeces, weighed on scales, to 9ml of buffered peptone water (BPW).
- D) If rectal swab, streak swab according to protocol for *E. coli*, and then place tip of swab in a 9ml buffered peptone water solution.
- E) Homogenise solution using a microloop.
- F) Incubate for 24 hours at 37°C along with the environmental samples (these are swabs which have been collected and placed in BPW whilst in the field)

Day 2

SUMMARY: Incubate all samples in selective enrichment broth

- G) Add 0.1ml of faecal-BPW solution to 9.9ml RV solution.
- H) Incubate RV and faecal material solution at 42°C for 24 hours.
- I) Storage: store 2ml of Buffered peptone water in a sterile cryovial with a barcode, log this and freeze at -80 degrees Celcius.

Day 3

SUMMARY: Inoculate plates

- J) Inoculate one petri dish of **Harlequin ABC Salmonella agar/CASE agar** and one petri dish of **XLD** with one sterile microloop of inoculum from each sample of RV broth.
- K) Incubate the plates at 37°C for 18-24 hours.

Day 4

SUMMARY: Culture positive colonies either onto nutrient agar, or subculture onto XLD/Harlequin agar

- L) Examine the plates for typical colonies (Figure 1a) and 1b) below).
- M) If culture is positive and pure positive colonies can be obtained, take picks of up to **5 separate colonies** of an isolate and culture onto nutrient agar at 37°C for 24hr.
- N) If it is not possible to take individual pure colonies, **subculture 5** possible positive isolates each onto half a plate of XLD or Harlequin ABC at 37°C for 24hr, then carry out stage L) until a pure culture has been obtained.

Day 5

SUMMARY: Serotyping

- O) Once pure cultures have been grown on nutrient agar, serotyping with O and poly H antigens should be carried out (see section 2).

Typical appearance of colonies to aid *Salmonella* identification

Typical Colonies XLD

Organism	Appearance
<i>Salmonella, Edwardsiella</i>	Red colonies with black centre
<i>Shigella, Providencia, H₂S-negative Salmonella</i> (eg <i>S paratyphi A</i>)	Red colonies
<i>Escherichia, Enterobacter, Klebsiella,</i> <i>Citrobacter, Proteus, Serratia</i>	Yellow, opaque colonies

Typical Colonies CASE Salmonella agar

Organism	Colony Size (mm)	Colour	Other
<i>Salmonella</i> spp	1.5 – 3.5	Green	(Black if galactosidase +ve)
<i>Shigella</i>	3.0 – 4.0	Colourless	(Black if galactosidase +ve)
<i>E. coli</i>	pp – 2.5	Black (No Growth)	
<i>Proteus</i> spp.	pp – 1.0	Colourless	(Fishy Odour)

2. Latex agglutination to confirm presence of *Salmonella*

All suspected *Salmonella* isolates will be tested with the following antisera:

- Polyvalent O (PL6002)
- Polyvalent H (PL6100)

Should these antisera yield positive results, further antisera testing with Hd and Vi antisera will be undertaken.

If the polyvalent O antisera give negative results test with the Vi antisera only. Vi is heat labile and can mask somatic antigen activity. It is mainly expressed by *S typhi* and more rarely by *S paratyphi C* strains. *Salmonella* expressing this antigen are not agglutinated by O antisera. Therefore, if a positive reaction with Vi is observed, heat the bacterial suspension to 100°C for 30 minutes, then repeat the test with Polyvalent O antisera.

Polyvalent H antisera looks at the flagella antigen, which are either Phase 1 or Phase 2. Hd antigen positive strains are Phase 1.

Method for *Salmonella* antisera testing:

1. Bring the reagents to room temperature.
2. Mix the suspensions by vigorous shaking. Expel any excess latex from the dropper pipettes to ensure complete mixing.
3. Place two separate drops of saline on a clean, dry microscope slide.
4. Using a microloop, add one pure colony of suspected *Salmonella* from **nutrient agar** onto each drop of saline and mix using a microloop.
5. Place one free falling drop of antisera onto the saline-isolate solution, and a second drop onto the saline, to be used as a control.
6. Mix the reagents thoroughly using the microloop.
7. Rock the slide in a circular motion for 30s and observe for agglutination.
8. Agglutination should occur in the test culture solution between 1-10s. If agglutination occurs >60s, the antigens cannot be identified correctly.

NB: In some cases, agglutination of both the test and control may be observed. Such results should be regarded as uninterpretable and unable to be serotyped. In these cases the culture should be re-streaked and checked using biochemical and serological procedures, or submitted for whole genome sequencing.

If agglutination of the test strain is present, carry out antimicrobial susceptibility testing via disc diffusion, and freeze isolate in microbank to bring back to the UK for genomic analysis.

Antisera	Antigen present if positive result
Polyvalent O (PL6002)	<i>Salmonella</i>
Polyvalent H (PL6100)	HMA-HG group present <i>Salmonella</i> present
Vi (PL6040)	<i>S. Typhi</i> , <i>S. Paratyphi</i> , <i>S. Dublin</i>
Hd (PL6113)	H antigen Phase 1 (Livingstone, Stanley, Muenchen)

3. **E. coli isolation** (Max number of samples per day=50)

E. coli culture will take place to determine the presence of commensal *E. coli* as well as pathogenic *E. coli* 0157 and other O groups of STEC.

Day 1

SUMMARY:

- **Human and animal: Inoculate plates directly with stool and incubate**
- **Environmental samples: Incubate in enrichment broth**

A) Human and animal stool samples:

- a. Using one clean microloop for each petri dish, inoculate one petri dish of **sorbitol MaConkey** agar and one plate of **MaConkey** agar with stool.
(If a faecal swab rather than stool sample has been taken, use this swab to inoculate both plates)
- b. Incubate for 24 hours at 37°C.

B) Environmental samples:

- c. Incubate the pre-collected swab and BPW solution in collection bag for 24 hours at 37°C.

Day 2

SUMMARY:

- **Human and animal: Read the Sorbitol MaConkey and MaConkey plates and plate onto TBX and/or MaConkey agar**
- **Environmental: Inoculate plates with enriched broth**

A) Human and animal stool samples

1. Reading Sorbitol MaConkey agar (we are assuming approx. 3% prevalence of *E. coli* 0157):
 - I. **Clear/colourless colonies-** take up to 5 colonies. Take **half** of each individual colony and place onto one plate of TBX agar and the other half onto **half a plate of MaConkey** agar.
 - II. **Pink colonies-** take 5 picks of these colonies and plate onto **half a plate of TBX** agar each.
2. Reading MaConkey agar:
 - I. **Pink colonies-** Plate 5 pink colonies onto half a plate of **TBX** agar each.

3. Incubate TBX and MaConkey plates for 24 hours at 37°C.

B) Environmental samples:

1. Using one clean microloop for each petri dish, inoculate one petri dish of **sorbitol MaConkey** agar and one plate of **MaConkey** agar with broth from the environmental enrichment.
2. Incubate for 24 hours at 37°C.

Day 3

SUMMARY:

- **Human and animal: Read the TBX and MaConkey plates and store in microbank tubes**
- **Environmental: Read the Sorbitol MaConkey and MaConkey plates and plate into TBX and/or MaConkey**

A) Human and animal stool samples

1. Findings of 5 colonies suspected as O157 on sorbitol MaConkey agar:
 - I. Reading MaConkey: Store up to 5 suspected O157 (pink)
 - II. Reading TBX: Store up to 5 suspected O157 (white/no growth)
2. Findings of 5 colonies suspected as non-pathogenic E coli on MaConkey agar:
 - I. TBX: Store up to 5 picks of suspected non-pathogenic *E. coli* (blue)
3. Storage:

Individual isolates

- I. Up to 5 colonies of each original human and animal sample will be stored.
- II. If it is not possible to take individual pure colonies, **subculture 5** possible positive isolates each on MaConkey at 37°C for 24hr, then repeat this until a pure culture has been obtained.
- III. Store each individual colony in a microbank tube, appropriately labelled (See Section).

Plate sweep

- IV. In addition to this take one plate sweep from each MaConkey plate. Store a sweep from the MaConkey plate in a microbank tube – take a microbiologic loop and sweep across the plate, picking up multiple colonies. If there is more than one colony colour or morphology, make sure that you pick up one of each type.

B) Environmental samples

1. Reading sorbitol MaConkey agar:

- I. **Clear/colourless colonies-** take up to 5 colonies. Take **half** of each individual colony and place onto one plate of **TBX** agar and the other half onto **half a plate of MaConkey** agar.
 - II. **Pink colonies-** take 5 picks of these colonies and plate each colony onto **half a plate of TBX** agar.
2. Reading MaConkey agar:
- III. **Pink colonies-** Plate 5 pink colonies onto half a plate of **TBX** agar each.
3. Incubate TBX and MaConkey plates for 24 hours at 37°C.

Day 4

SUMMARY:

- **Environmental:** Read the TBX and MaConkey plates and store in microbank tubes

A) Environmental samples

1. Findings of 5 colonies suspected as O157 on sorbitol MaConkey agar:
 - I. Reading MaConkey: Store up to 5 suspected O157 (pink)
 - II. Reading TBX: Store up to 5 suspected O157 (white/no growth)

2. Findings of 5 colonies suspected as non-pathogenic E coli on MaConkey agar:
 - I. TBX: Store up to 5 suspected non-pathogenic *E. coli* (blue)

Individual isolates

- I. Up to 5 colonies of each original human and animal sample will be stored.
- II. If it is not possible to take individual pure colonies, **subculture 5** possible positive isolates each on MaConkey at 37°C for 24hr, then repeat this until a pure culture has been obtained.
- III. Store each individual colony in a microbank tube, appropriately labelled (See Section).

Plate sweep

- IV. In addition to this take one plate sweep from each MaConkey plate. Store a sweep from the MaConkey plate in a microbank tube – take a microbiologic loop and sweep across the plate, picking up multiple colonies. If there is more than one colony colour or morphology, make sure that you pick up one of each type.

Typical appearance of colonies to aid *E. coli* identification

Typical colonies Sorbitol MaConkey agar

Organism	Appearance
<i>E. coli</i> O157	colourless

Other <i>E. coli</i>	Pink
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Typical colonies MaConkey agar

Organism	Colour	Remarks
<i>E. coli</i>	red	Non-muroid
<i>Aerobacter aerogenes</i>	pink	Muroid
<i>Enterococcus</i> species	red	Minute, round
<i>Staphylococcus</i> species	Pale pink	Opaque
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Green-brown	Fluorescent growth

Typical colonies of TBX (tryptone bile X-Glucuronide medium) agar

Organism	Colour
<i>E. coli</i>	Blue/green
<i>E. coli</i> 0157	White/no growth
Other bacteria	Colourless

4. Microbank Inoculation

1. Label a separate Microbank™ vial corresponding to the correct number in the database for each organism to be stored.
2. Using aseptic technique, unscrew the Microbank™ vial cap.
3. Using a sterile inoculating loop or cotton swab, pick off enough colonies from a pure culture to achieve a 3-4 McFarland standard in the cryopreservative. (In general, an overnight culture (18-24 hours) of the isolate is preferred)
4. Using aseptic technique, replace the cap on the Microbank™ vial tightly and invert it 4-5 times to emulsify the organism. DO NOT VORTEX!
5. Let the Microbank™ vial sit for 2 minutes to allow the isolate to bind to the beads. Remove the cap and use a sterile disposable pasteur pipette to remove the cryopreservative. The beads should be as free of liquid as possible.
6. Close the Microbank™ vial finger tight only. It is important that the Microbank™ vials are not overtightened.
7. Place the Microbank™ vial in a Microbank™ Freezer Storage Box and freeze at -70°C.

5. Recovery of *Salmonella* and *E. coli* Isolates

1. Remove the Microbank™ vial from the -70°C freezer and place it in a cold cryoblock (PL.155-1).
2. Using aseptic technique, open the Microbank™ vial and using a sterile needle, or forceps remove one coloured bead. Close the Microbank™ vial finger tight and return as soon as possible to the freezer. Excessive changes in temperature will reduce the viability of the frozen isolates.
3. The bead may then be streaked directly onto a solid medium or may be inoculated into an appropriate liquid medium.

5 Antimicrobial Resistance Testing

Method

1. Remove the container of antibiotic disks from the freezer or refrigerator. *Before opening the container*, allow the disks to equilibrate to room temperature for 1-2 hours to minimize condensation and reduce the possibility of moisture affecting the concentration of antimicrobial agents.
2. Allow the Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA) plate to warm to room temperature so that any excess moisture will be absorbed into the medium. You can expedite this step by placing the plates in the incubator with their lids ajar for 10–15 minutes. Ensure the MHA plate agar is 4 mm deep.
3. Take 3-5 isolated, pure colonies of an individual strain of *Salmonella* or *E. coli* grown on nutrient agar. Using an inoculating loop pick only well-isolated colonies from the plate to avoid testing mixed cultures. If you do not have well-isolated colonies, subculture the organism to a fresh plate.
4. Add these colonies to 1ml 0.9% sterile saline solution in plastic bijous.
5. Using the direct colony suspension method, the turbidity of the test suspension must be standardized to match that of a 0.5 McFarland standard (corresponds to approximately 1.5×10^8 cfu/ml).
6. The adjusted suspensions should be used as inocula **within 15 minutes** of creation.
7. Vortex the organism suspension to make sure it is well-mixed. Then, dip a fresh, sterile cotton-tipped swab into the suspension. Remove the excess liquid from the swab by pressing it against the side of the tube.
8. Starting at the top of the MHA plate inoculate the surface with the swab. Cover the entire plate by streaking back and forth from edge to edge. Rotate the plate approximately 60° and repeat the swabbing procedure. Rotate the plate 60° again and swab the entire plate a third time. This will ensure that the inoculum is evenly distributed.
9. Apply the 6 discs containing the antimicrobial agents **within 15 minutes of inoculating** the MHA plate. Disks may be placed on the plate one at a time or with a multichannel disk dispenser.
10. Press each disk down firmly to ensure complete, level contact with the agar. Don't forget this step or disks may end up in the lid of the plate after incubation.
11. Invert and incubate plates with agar side up at 35°C for 16–18 hours.
12. Following removal of the plate from the incubator examine the plate closely to make certain the lawn of growth is even and confluent so you can see unobstructed zones.

To measure zones from the back of the plate using reflected light:

13. Hold the plate a few inches above a black nonreflecting surface.
14. Measure the diameter of the zone of inhibition to the nearest millimeter with a ruler or calipers.
15. Any colonies growing within the zones of inhibition should be subcultured and identified, and the antimicrobial susceptibility test repeated if necessary.

16. Compare the diameter of the zone of inhibition to the EUCAST breakpoints to determine if the isolate is resistant, susceptible or has intermediate resistance to each of the six antibiotics.

Making agar and broths

1) Buffered Peptone Water

1. Weigh **20 grams** of powder and disperse in 1 litre of deionised water.
 2. Mix to dissolve then distribute into tubes or bottles.
 3. Sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
- **Appearance:** Pale straw, clear liquid.
 - **pH:** 7.2 ± 0.2
 - **Minimum Q.C. organisms:** E. coli WDCM 00090
 - **Storage of Prepared Medium:** Capped containers – up to 3 months at 15-20°C in the dark.
 - **Inoculation:** Add 25 grams of sample to 225ml of Buffered Peptone Water and homogenise.
 - **Incubation:** Aerobically at 37°C for 18-24 hours.

2) Rappaport Vassiliadis broth

1. Weigh **27.14 grams** of powder, and add to 1 litre of deionised water.
 2. Swirl to dissolve.
 3. Distribute into bottles or tubes, and sterilise at 115°C for 15 minutes.
- **Incubation:** 30-35°C for 18-24 hours.
 - **Appearance Powder:** fine, free-flowing, homogeneous, buff to light green
 - **Finished medium:** Blue, clear to slight haze
 - **pH:** 5.2 ± 0.2
 - Hazard classification Xi – Irritant
 - **Storage Dehydrated culture media:** 10-25oC away from direct sunlight.
 - **Prepared media:** Up to 7 days at 2-8°C in the dark.
 - Minimum Q.C. organisms
 - *Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhimurium* ATCC 14028 Good Growth
 - *Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Abony* NCTC 6017 Good Growth
 - *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 Inhibited

Interpretation

Growth characteristics		
Organism	Expected result in RV broth	Expected result on XLD subculture
<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	Turbid Growth	Growth, typical colonies
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	No Visible Growth	No Growth

Note any growth should be confirmed by further identification tests.

3) CASE Salmonella Agar

Method for reconstitution

1. Weigh **49.9 grams** of powder, disperse in 1 litre of deionised water.
2. Allow the mixture to soak for 10 minutes, swirl to mix.
3. Bring rapidly to the boil with frequent agitation.
4. Cool to 50°C in water bath, mix well and dispense into Petri dishes.

DO NOT REMELT OR AUTOCLAVE THIS MEDIUM

Appearance: Translucent straw gel.

pH: 7.2 ± 0.2

Minimum QC organisms: *Salmonella typhimurium* WDCM 00031

Escherichia coli WDCM 00013

Storage of Prepared Medium: Plates - up to 7 days at 2 - 8°C in the dark.

Incubation: 37°C aerobically for 18 - 24 hours

GROWTH CHARACTERISTICS				
Organism	Colony Size (mm)	Shape & Surface	Colour	Other
<i>Salmonella</i> spp	1.5 – 3.5	C.V.E.G	Green	(Black if galactosidase +ve)
<i>Shigella</i>	3.0 – 4.0	C.V.E.G	Colourless	(Black if galactosidase +ve)
<i>E. coli</i>	pp – 2.5	C.V.E.G	Black (No Growth)	
<i>Proteus</i> spp.	pp – 1.0	C.V.E.G	Colourless	(Fishy Odour)

4) XLD Agar:

1. Suspend **53g** in 1 litre of distilled water.
2. Heat with frequent agitation until the medium boils.
3. **DO NOT OVERHEAT.**
4. Transfer immediately to a water bath at 50°C.
5. Pour into sterile Petri dishes as soon as the medium has cooled.

Store the dehydrated medium at 10-30°C and use before the expiry date on the label.

Store the prepared medium at 2-8°C.

pH 7.4+/- 0.2@25°C

Appearance of prepared medium: Red coloured gel

Organism	Appearance
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<i>Salmonella, Edwardsiella</i>	Red colonies with black centre
<i>Shigella, Providencia, H2S-negative Salmonella (eg S paratyphi A)</i>	Red colonies
<i>Escherichia, Enterobacter, Klebsiella, Citrobacter, Proteus, Serratia</i>	Yellow, opaque colonies

- Red colonies may also occur with some *Proteus* and *Pseudomonas*

4) Nutrient Agar

1. Weigh **28 grams** of powder, disperse in 1 litre of deionised water.
2. Allow to soak for 10 minutes, swirl to mix then sterilise by autoclaving for 15 minutes at 121°C.
3. Cool to 47°C, mix well then pour plates.

Appearance: Buff, opalescent gel.

pH: 7.3 ± 0.2

Minimum Q.C. organisms: *S. aureus* WDCM 00034 *E. coli* WDCM 00031

Storage of Prepared Medium: Plates – up to 7 days at 2-8°C in the dark. Capped containers – up to 3 months at 15-20°C in the dark.

Inoculation: Surface streaking for single colonies.

Incubation: Temperature and time to suit organisms. Usually aerobic.

Growth Characteristics				
Organism	Colony size (mm)	Shape & surface	Colour	Other
<i>S. aureus</i>	1.0-2.0	CV.E.G.	White-Yellow	
<i>Other Staphylococcus spp</i>	0.5-2.0	CV.E.G.	White.Yellow	
<i>Strep. pyogenes</i>	P.P.-0.5	CV.E.G	Transp.	
<i>E. coli</i>	1.5-2.5	CV.E.G.	Grey	
<i>Bacillus spp</i>	2.0-6.0	various	Grey	may spread
<i>Ps. Aeruginosa</i>	2.0-4.0	F.CR.D.	Grey-Green	odour if pigmented

5) Mueller-Hinton Agar

1. Weigh **38 grams** of powder, disperse in 1 litre of deionised water.
2. Allow to soak for 10 minutes, swirl to mix then sterilise at 121°C for 15 minutes.
3. Cool to 47°C, mix well and pour plates.

Appearance: Straw coloured, clear gel.

pH: 7.3 ± 0.1

Minimum Q.C. organisms: *E. coli* WDCM 00013 *S. aureus* (antibiotic sensitivity zones) WDCM 00034

Storage of Prepared Medium: Plates – up to 7 days at 2-8°C in the dark.

Inoculation: Surface, inoculum as described by N.C.C.L.S.

Incubation: As recommended by methodology for particular organisms and antibiotics by NCCLS. (See saved print out: Manual of Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing)

6) Tryptone bile X-glucuronide medium (TBX)

1. Suspend **36.6g** of TBX Medium in 1 litre of distilled water.
2. Sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
3. Cool to 50°C and pour the medium into sterile Petri dishes.

pH 7.2 +/- 0.2@ 25°C

Appearance; straw coloured gel

Store prepared plates at 2-8°C

Incubate at 37°C for 18-24 hours

Organism	Colour
<i>E. coli</i>	Blue/green

7) MaConkey agar

1. Suspend 52g in 1 litre of distilled water.
2. Bring to the boil to dissolve completely.
3. Sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
4. Dry the surface of the gel before inoculation.

pH 7.4+/- 0.2

Appearance dark red coloured gel

Store 2-8°C

Incubate at 35-37°C for 24 hours

Organism	Colour	Remarks
<i>E. coli</i>	Red	Non-mucoid
<i>Aerobacter aerogenes</i>	Pink	Mucoid
<i>Enterococcus</i> spp.	Red	Minute, round
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	Pale pink	Opaque
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Green-brown	Fluorescent growth

8) Sorbitol MaConkey agar

1. Suspend 51.5g in 1 litre of distilled water.
2. Bring to the boil to dissolve completely.
3. Sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
4. Allow to cool to 50°C.
5. Pour into sterile Petri dishes.

pH 7.1 +/-0.2 @25°C

Incubation at 35-37°C for 24 hours.

Storage: prepared media can be stored for up to two weeks at 2-8°C out of direct sunlight.

Appearance: prepared media: dark red gel.

Number of plates to prepare prior to a sampling week

Type of media	Number per sample	Number (30 samples)
Buffered peptone water	9ml	270ml
Rappaport Vassiliadis	9.9ml	300ml
Sorbitol MaConkey	1 plate	30 plates (+some extra)
MaConkey	4 plates	120 plates (+some extra)
XLD	1 plate	30 plates (+some extra)
TBX	8 plates	240 plates (+some extra)
Harlequin ABC agar/CASE	1 plate	30 plates (+some extra)
Nutrient agar	5 plates	150 plates
Mueller Hinton	25 plates	750 plates?!

Make Your Own Freeze Media for microbank tubes

To preserve bacterial isolates for future use, prepare a freeze matrix and aliquot to sterile cryovials (with O-ring cap is best). Use LB (Luria-Bretani) broth, BHI (Brain Heart Infusion) broth, or TSB (Tryptic Soy Broth) and add sterile glycerol to create a final concentration of 30% sterile glycerol (v/v) as the matrix.

The glycerol is heavy so mix well when working. Aseptically add about 1mL of the mix to the cryovials and store at 4° C. After inoculation with a loop of fresh culture, freeze the same vial at -20° C. The matrix won't freeze completely hard but remains slushy due to the glycerol.

To subculture from frozen stock, stab a hot loop into the vial while keeping the sample as cold as possible. Streak the inoculum to the appropriate plate medium. Immediately refreeze the vial. Freeze thaw cycles decrease the viability of the bacteria. Complete thawing of the sample may require a new preparation from a fresh subculture. Additional information about cryopreservation of microorganisms can be found at the ATCC website (www.atcc.com)

Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) Preparation:

- I. Add 30g of tryptic soy broth (TSB) to 950 mL of deionized water, mix thoroughly, and heat to dissolve completely. Bring the volume up to 1L with deionized water.
- II. Adjust pH to 7.3 ± 0.2 with 1.0 N HCl or 1.0 N NaOH.
- III. Add 200mL of Glycerol
- IV. Dispense 1.2mL of the solution into each cryovial
- V. Autoclave for at 121°C for 15 minutes.

Storage: 4°C for up to 6 months.

5. HEALTH AND SAFETY

Follow Health and Safety guidelines as laid out in the MLW Health and Safety Manual

- Contact with animals will occur which may be carrying a variety of zoonotic and infectious diseases.
- Non-typhoidal *Salmonella* and *E. coli* are potentially zoonotic diseases transmitted via the faeco-oral route, therefore appropriate personal protective equipment (nitrile gloves, wellies, coveralls) will be worn to prevent infection when handling faecal samples.
- Appropriate hygiene methods will be undertaken for example washing hands prior to leaving the sampling sites.
- Care will be taken to use appropriate methods of restraint when working with animals.

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7. APPENDICES

Equipment required for sample collection

- MLW vehicle
- 2x Tablet to carry out household questionnaire and gain consent
- Clipboard
- Paper
- Paper copies of HH questionnaire
- Barcodes to attach to faecal sample pots
- Pens to write on paper
- Pens to write on faecal sample pots
- 40x faecal sample pots
- Zip lock bags (to store samples in whilst awaiting collection- advise store in the fridge)
- Multiple coloured dots to identify origin of sample?
- 10x Corrugated paper collection pots
- 15x Stomacher/sterile bags to collect flies
- 1 box nitrile gloves
- Halter
- 4x pairs Wellington boots (dependent on number helping)
- 4x Coveralls (dependent on number helping)
- 3x Dog Muzzle (different sizes)
- Serum blood vacutainers?
- Sterile needles
- 1 box x KY jelly/other sterile lubricant- sachets
- 4x Large waterproof tarpaulin
- 2x Bird nets
- 4x Sticks to erect bird nets
- Twine to erect bird nets
- 1x Quick unpick
- 2x African bird sounds recording and music player
- 2 pairs gauntlets/anti-cut gloves
- 30x Sterile amies swabs for cloacal sampling (may be too many)
- Look into tracheal swab to collect and store saliva from birds?
- 20x pairs of bootsocks (may be too many)
- 4x large humane rat traps
- Bait (cheese for rat traps)
- 4x pictures of gecko faeces
- Large transparent plastic container to collect flies

- 1x packet of stomacher bags to collect flies
- BPW swabs to collect environmental swabs from areas around household, hands, latrine areas, chitengis
- Cooler box
- Ice packs
- Virkon to disinfect wellington boots
- Water in container for washing
- Water container
- Scrubbing brush
- Bucket to wash boots
- Rubbish bags to collect coveralls
- Tweezers
- Tick remover

i) Equipment list Salmonella and E. coli isolation

- Glass bijoux bottles
- Buffered peptone water
- Rappaport vassiliadis broth
- CASE agar
- XLD agar
- TBX agar
- MaConkey agar
- Sorbitol MaConkey agar
- Nutrient agar
- Microloops
- Incubator 37°C
- 9ml, 10ml and 9.9ml pipette- electronic pipette
- Pipette tips
- 0.1ml sterile pipette syringe RVS
- 42°C incubator/water bath
- Petri dishes

ii) Equipment for slide agglutination

- Microscope slides
- *Salmonella* anti-sera (Prolab)
 - PL6002 Polyvalent O
 - PL6100 Polyvalent H
 - PL6113 Hd
 - PL6040 Vi
- Black surface to rest slide on
- Microloop

- Saline
- Pipette to draw up saline
- Timer

iii) **Equipment list for microbank storage**

- Microbank tubes (premade up) up to 250 per household
- Equipment to make up own microbank tubes
 - Sterile cryovials
 - Tryptone soy broth

iv) **Equipment list for antimicrobial susceptibility testing**

- Microloops
- Sterile saline
- Sterile plastic up to 5ml container
- Nutrient agar plates
- Mueller Hinton agar plates
- Distilled water
- Sterile cotton swab
- Sharpie
- Multi-channel antibiotic dispenser
- Antibiotic discs: tetracycline, streptomycin, amoxicillin, ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, chloramphenicol

General Lab Equipment Required

- Virkon powder
- Blue roll
- Spray bottles
- Weighing scales
- Heat plate and magnetic stirrer
- Conical flask
- Spatula
- Cool box
- Ice blocks
- Distilled water
- Sharpies
- pH meter
- Measuring cylinder

9. TRAINING RECORD FOR THIS SOP

The following have been trained in this SOP and have demonstrated adequate knowledge of its contents:

Name of Trainee	Name of Trainer	Signature/Date of Trainee	Signature/Date of Trainer